

Madagascar: The economics of HIV

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Key points

- US\$1 invested in ending AIDS in Madagascar by 2030 generates a net return on investment of US\$4.
- Failing to achieve the AIDS target by 2030 will result in a cumulative total cost of inaction of US\$3.84 billion in economic and social loss to the Malagasy people
- The human cost of inaction in achieving the AIDS Target could cumulate to nearly 45.35 thousand additional HIV infections and 12.86 thousand additional AIDS-related deaths by 2030
- Ignoring or failing to meet the 10-10-10 Targets could represent a cumulated economic cost of US\$77.50 by 2030 and US\$293.59 per capita by 2050
- HIV domestic expenditures, although low in numerical terms (US\$290k in 2017), still represent 2.20% of its GDP.
- Negotiations based on funding, including donors and domestic shares, are unlikely to find a sustainable equilibrium to reach the AIDS Targets in Madagascar.
- Instead, commitments on number of new infections or people on ART could be a promising alternate commitment, with midterm milestones matching with key donors planning horizon.
- Madagascar bears almost all the cost of inaction but only part of the cost of action.

The economic benefits of ending AIDS: Rate of return and cost of inaction:

Using the full-income approachⁱ to valuing the mortality reduction of the HIV Targets in Madagascar, each additional US dollar of national and international resources invested between 2021 and 2030 generatesⁱⁱ net return on investment (RoI) worth US\$4.0 through 2030, rising to US\$5.0 by 2050.ⁱⁱⁱ For each Malagasy citizen, the cost of inaction (CoI) induced by the lost lives and other benefits foregone by not increasing HIV spending greatly outweigh savings from the avoided HIV spending, with the average Malagasy losing US\$89 through 2030 (about 15% of GDP per capita) increasing to US\$321 through 2050 (as much as 66% of current GDP per capita). (See Figure 1)

By 2030, RoI from global perspective:
US\$1 cost → US\$4 benefit

By 2030, CoI from global perspective:
Inaction costs each Malagasy US\$89
the equivalent of 15% of per capita GDP

Figure.7j. Return on investment and cost of inaction for the incremental HIV spending required to end HIV/AIDS as a public health threat in Madagascar; (Global social planner perspective)

Madagascar bears almost all the cost of inaction, but only part of the cost of action:

The human cost of inaction; By 2030, the human cost of inaction could reach nearly 45.35 thousand additional HIV infections and 12.86 thousand additional AIDS-related deaths compared to the case where the AIDS targets’ coverage in Madagascar is kept as it was in 2020. By 2050, the human cost of inaction could reach 220.36 thousand new HIV infections and 67.22 thousand additional HIV-related deaths. These human costs of inaction can be avoided by increasing HIV investment to achieve the agreed AIDS Targets in Madagascar.

The social consequences; The cost of inaction of failing to end AIDS also implies failing to end inequality. The foregone benefits include those affecting health, education and inequalities in gender, ethnicity, and other dimensions.

The return on investment from Madagascar's perspective. Assuming that Madagascar receives all the economic, human and social benefits from the incremental investments to end AIDS, but will bear only about 17% of the incremental cost, the return on the country’s investment rises from 4.0 through 2030 to 29, or by about 700%. This extraordinarily high national return on Madagascar’s contribution to its HIV spending is a strong argument for it to allocate sufficient funds to allow HIV prevention and treatment programs to reach their full potential.

The importance of the 10-10-10 Targets for Madagascar

The 10-10-10 targets are an integral part of the Ending AIDS, Ending Inequality Strategy. In Madagascar, the societal enablers represent between 14% and 20% of the resource needs estimates and have a tremendous impact on the benefits in terms of new HIV infections and HIV-related deaths averted, representing about a quarter (25%) of the health benefits in the early years. The 10-10-10 Targets in Madagascar produce a Return on Investment (RoI) of approximately 4:1. In other words, each US\$1 invested in the societal enablers in particular between now and 2030 generates US\$4.1 in health, economic and social benefits.

US\$1 in 10-10-10 → US\$4.1 benefit

Inaction in 10-10-10 → cost US\$77 per Malagasy by 2030

Ignoring or failing to meet the 10-10-10 targets could represent a cumulated economic cost of US\$77.50 by 2030 and US\$293.59 per capita by 2050. The human cost of ignoring societal enablers in Madagascar could represent 9.52 thousand additional HIV infections and 2.32 thousand additional AIDS-related deaths. By 2050, the human cost of inaction could reach 46.28 thousand new HIV infections and 12.01 thousand additional HIV-related deaths.

The economists' insight

Madagascar is a low-income country with a GDPpc of US\$588. The country faces severe fiscal space constraints, particularly due to rising fiscal deficits. Nevertheless, recent studies suggest that Madagascar's tax potential is greater than 6% of GDP, i.e. Madagascar's potential to increase its fiscal space is larger than the average SSA countries (4.8-5.5% of GDP)^{iv}

Its average contribution to the AIDS response for 2015-2017, the three most recent years reported in GAM is 16.9%^v. This share is higher than several ESA low-income countries like Zimbabwe (2.5%), Mozambique (3.5%), and Tanzania (1.2%), a middle-income country. Recent intelligence suggests that Madagascar's domestic share of the AIDS response could have fallen as low as 5% to 8% in the recent few years, meaning that the AIDS response is even more underfunded, leading to AIDS Targets being off track and the country's AIDS transition point not foreseen before 2030^{vi}.

It is worth noting that HIV domestic expenditures, although low in numerical terms (US\$290k in 2017),^{vii} still represented 2.20% of its GDP.

Given the above elements and the opportunity cost of HIV spending in terms of other alternative spending needs, the economic game theory suggests that Madagascar may try to leverage its situation as bargaining power, positioning itself as doing not-so-bad, if not better, relative to its economic capacity and pushing against further increasing its contribution. The Malagasy Ministries of Finances (MoF) and Health (MoH) would be rational in trying to ensure the largest possible share of funding from donors and an as small as possible share from domestic sources.

Considering the AIDS response as a public good, Madagascar could argue that additional financing should come from wealthier nations or be provided through debt relief, for example. This creates a "free rider" situation, where the Malagasy government reaps all the benefits without paying its fair share.

The principal agent problem brings light to another issue: Madagascar's donor community faces moral hazard; the country has little incentive to invest more because it expects donors to bear the cost of the AIDS response anyway. There is a risk that the government prioritises other national priorities or political goals over investing in the AIDS response, knowing that donors are unlikely to withdraw their support. Donors, on the other hand, can hardly commit beyond their respective planning cycles.

It appears that neither party has power to commit through 2030, much less over the longer term. This imbalance suggests potential inefficiencies of the current setup and poses a long-term threat to Madagascar's AIDS response.

Negotiations based on funding, including donors and domestic shares, are unlikely to find a sustainable equilibrium to reach the AIDS Targets in Madagascar. Instead, commitments on number of new infections or people on ART could be a promising alternate commitment, with midterm milestones matching with key donors planning horizon^{viii}.

There are economic incentives to support such alternative commitments: the cost of inaction represents US\$16.78 billion in economic losses by 2050, which is the equivalent of Madagascar's GDP in 2023 (US\$16.03 billion)^{ix}, along with 220,000 new HIV infections and over 67,000 AIDS-related deaths, making the idle position of the Malagasy government unsustainable in the medium (2030) to long term (2050).

Furthermore, the benefit cost analysis shows that each US\$1 invested in ending AIDS between now and 2030 generates US\$4 in economic return (RoI). Moreover, from the Malagasy government's perspective, each dollar invested from its budget between 2021 and 2030 brings a higher return, reaching up to US\$25 per dollar invested in the current situation.

In other words, while Madagascar may rationally argue for more external funding or debt relief, its current commitment to the AIDS response is not sustainable, particularly because the country will be alone in bearing the economic, human and societal costs of inaction. Commitment mechanisms other than financial may offer promising solutions, in addition to the high return on investment in the AIDS response for the Malagasy government. These factors could encourage the government to reassess its position and take greater ownership of its AIDS response.

Notes:

ⁱ Empirical studies argue that health can, in fact, be valued, for example, in dollar terms, and added to other components of a nation's production to arrive at a "full_income" measure of economic well-being. In other terms, the social value of increasing the life expectancy of an individual for, say, one year exceeds the economic value of his or her productivity. See the study referenced below for more details.

ⁱⁱ Costs are a function of countries' people on ART, people who are HIV negative, the type of epidemic, economic output per capita, and region, after controlling per year and allowing interactions between variables. $F(23, 1266)=1111.03$, $\text{Prob} >F = .0000$, $R^2 = 0.95$. Incremental costs are valued in US (constant, 2019) dollars and US international (PPP, constant, 2019) dollars for the tradeable and non-tradeable components of costs, respectively. Incremental benefits from the difference between the Target Scenario reflecting the 2021-2026 HIV Strategy and a counterfactual scenario where coverage is kept constant as of the 2020 coverage rate. Benefits valued in international (PPP, constant, 2019) dollars.

The cumulative cost of inaction for the period 2021-2050, per capita and total, for each region. The cost of inaction is presented from the national perspective, i.e., the national Ministry of Finances only considers the cost incurred nationally.

Benefit and cost are discounted, $(r) = 0.03$. US ratio of VSL to GDPpc = 120

Central values of the RoI and CoI assume an income elasticity $\eta = 1.0$.

Sensitivity analysis: the lower bound assumes income elasticity $\eta = 1.2$, and the upper bound assumes $\eta = 0.8$.

ⁱⁱⁱ Range of the 2030 RoI is 2 to 7, with a central value of 4.

^{iv} Source: IMF, Tax Revenue mobilisation potential in Madagascar and lessons from successful episodes in SSA, 2020
^v 16.9% corresponds to the mean of the national AIDS spending for the three most recent years reported (2016-2017-2019). Source: GAM, July 2024

^{vi} Mead Over, Achieving an AIDS Transition: Preventing infections to sustain treatment, Brookings Institution, 2011

^{vii} Source: GAM, July 2024. Last accessed date: 10 Oct.2024

^{viii} Ibid

^{ix} Source: The World Bank, <https://data.worldbank.org/>

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